

PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY AND PERFORMANCE OF OIL AND GAS FUNDED PROJECTS IN NIGER DELTA REGION OF SOUTH SOUTH, NIGERIA

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Article Info

Keywords: Project Implementation Strategy, Oil and Gas Performance, Niger Delta Region, Strategy Implementation, Project Design

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.10063798

Abstract

The researcher aimed to examine the relationship between project implementation strategy and the performance of oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria. The specific objectives are as follows: to assess the extent of the relationship between project design and the performance of oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria, and to determine the extent of the relationship between project monitoring and the performance of oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria. The researcher adopted a survey research design. The total population of the study was 1,272,000, drawn from two selected local government areas in Delta State, namely Warri and Burutu. The sample size for the study was 400, determined using Taro Yamane's statistical formula. Spearman's rank correlation method was employed to test hypotheses. The findings indicated that project design had a significant positive relationship with the performance of oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria ($r=0.458$, $p<0.05$), and project monitoring had a significant positive relationship with the performance of oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria ($r=0.457$, $p<0.05$). The study concluded that project implementation strategy has a significant positive relationship with the performance of oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommends that contractors responsible for oil and gas-funded projects should prioritize the identification of key elements necessary for designing and monitoring projects to benefit the government and stakeholders in the communities. in teaching the students.

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INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The Nigerian oil and gas industry has been thriving since the discovery of crude oil in 1956 by the Shell Group. However, the sector was predominantly dominated by multinational corporations until the early 1990s when Nigerian companies began entering the industry. Local participation received a significant boost with the implementation of the Nigerian Content Directives issued by the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) about a decade ago and, ultimately, with the promulgation of the Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry Content Development (NOGIC) Act in 2010. The Act aims to promote the utilization of Nigerian resources and companies in the awarding of oil licenses, contracts, and projects (Effiong, 2014).

The Niger Delta faces significant environmental and social challenges due to issues such as oil spills, gas flaring, deforestation, decreasing land productivity, and pollution. The apparent lack of government and oil companies' responsiveness to these problems has led to unrest and agitation in host communities, demanding fair compensation and a more equitable share of the profits from the extraction of natural resources within their areas. However, these demands have become increasingly politicized and radicalized, resulting in violent actions such as hostage-taking and youth militancy, which have taken on criminal dimensions. These developments have profound implications for a nation heavily reliant on oil revenues (Effiong, 2014).

In 2006, Nigeria had a population of approximately 144.7 million (Energy Information Administration, 2006). According to the Federal Office of Statistics (1999), the poverty rate in Nigeria rose from 28% to 66% between 1980 and 1996. The gross domestic product (GDP) in 1982 was \$860 billion, which declined to \$280 billion in 1996 and stands at \$290 billion currently. Poverty levels have increased, with an estimated 49% of the urban population living in poverty. Nigeria is ranked among the 30 poorest countries globally. Many of the population are either underemployed or unemployed, with no means of livelihood. The Nigerian government conservatively estimates unemployment at 10.8%, but the World Bank suggests that 40-50% of those living in major urban centers and recent graduates are unemployed (World Bank, 2021).

The setting of strategy implementation is recognized by a growing number of oil and gas firms in today's world, given the increasingly competitive global market that demands agility and organization from these companies. Consequently, all oil and gas firms have their strategies established and documented to guide them in their long-term tasks (Latifa, 2011). However, the challenge lies in translating a selected strategy into actual actions. As a result, project management has become an essential approach for many organizations, as projects serve as tools for implementing organizational strategies. Projects within an organization contribute to the growth and development of the business's strategic plan (Latifa, 2011).

The International Finance Corporation (IFC), the private arm of the World Bank, conducted a research study and found that only half of its African projects succeeded, and many other donors had similarly disappointing results (Lavagnon, Amadou & Denis, 2022). The failure of these projects is attributed to the approach taken in their implementation. Project implementation strategy is an emerging concept in the research literature on project management (Patanakul, Shenhar & Milosevic, 2019). Project implementation strategies establish the boundaries for a project to meet its current and future goals and objectives (Longman & Mullins, 2021). The most successful project management organizations have clear, well-communicated strategies that support their projects.

The concept of oil and gas project performance has been discussed by researchers and practitioners, yet there is little consensus on the factors that distinguish a successful project from a failed one (Pinto & Slevin, 2019). However, there are common characteristics shared by all projects, and traditional criteria have been used by practitioners and researchers to assess project success (Pinto & Slevin, 2018). Shenhar, Levy, & Dvir (2017) argue that project performance is meaningful when considered from two perspectives: the degree to which the project meets its technical performance objectives on time and within budget, and the contribution that the project makes to the strategic mission of the organization (Prabhakar, 2018). Based on this background, this study deemed it necessary to investigate the relationship between project implementation strategy and the performance of oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria.

Project Implementation Strategy is crucial for the performance of oil and gas-funded projects. For an implementation strategy to result in superior performance, all the steps in the process need to be effectively managed. A well-crafted strategy can put an oil and gas project on the competitive map and enhance its performance. Unfortunately, many oil and gas project contractors struggle with implementation, leading to performance failures (Blahová & Knápková, 2019).

The main challenges faced by oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria include a mass exodus of staff, resulting in a weak human resource base, the government's inability to attract and retain essential skills needed to drive performance, the loss of value in oil and gas-funded projects as complementary public service providers, poor governance leading to resource mismanagement, and a lack of proper structures to link performance to national development programs. As the Federal Government becomes more focused on performance, oil and gas-funded projects are experiencing reduced funding. Many of these projects fail to achieve their strategic objectives and do not improve the lives of their intended beneficiaries. Consequently, these projects face increased criticism from the government and the public, with regulatory bodies calling for the closure of some government-approved oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region due to delayed completion.

However, there has been little empirical work in this area. A few examples include Ferreira, Vieira Neto, and Batista (2019), who examined critical success factors in project and process management in competitive strategy implementation in Brazil. Lucas (2019) studied strategy implementation practices and performance in international non-governmental organizations in Kenya, and Mukamugenga and Eugenia (2022) examined project implementation practices and project performance in Rwanda. However, there is inconsistency in their findings. It is essential to note that these studies lack adequate evidence to explain the determinants of project strategy implementation. Therefore, this research aims to fill the gap in understanding the relationship between project implementation strategy and the performance of oil and gas projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria. The main objective of the study is to investigate the relationship between project implementation strategy and the performance of oil and gas projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria, specifically to:

- i. Examine the extent of the relationship between project design and the performance of oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria.
- ii. Ascertain the extent of the relationship between project monitoring and the performance of oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria.

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study is to investigate the relationship between project implementation strategy and the performance of oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria. The study is limited to Niger Delta citizens aged 18 and above, as they possess more knowledge about oil and gas business activities in Nigeria, in accordance with the 2006 census population data. The study focuses on two specific local government areas, Warri and Burutu, out of a total of eight, including Warri, Burutu, Isoko, Ughelli, Okpe, Ethiope, Sapele, and Ndokwu. Specifically, the study concentrates on two project implementation strategies as independent variables: project design and project monitoring, while performance remains the dependent variable, which can be further analyzed in terms of cost, time, quality, and other factors.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Project

In this regard, projects are defined as "organizational units dedicated to the attainment of a goal, generally involving the successful completion of a developmental product on time, within budget, and in compliance with predetermined performance specifications" (Soderlund, 2018). British Standard 6079 (1996) defines a project as "a unique set of coordinated activities, with defined start and finish points, undertaken by individuals or organizations to achieve specific objectives within defined schedules, costs, and performance parameters."

Implementation

Implementation simply refers to the process of effectively leading, working with and through others, allocating resources, building and strengthening competitive capabilities, installing strategy-supportive policies, and

shaping how the organization conducts its core business activities (Enudu, 1999). Implementation involves translating the organization's strategic plan into action and, subsequently, into results.

Strategy

The term "strategy" was originally a military concept for describing a grand plan to win a war. However, today, businesses and organizations have adopted the term, making it a common part of the managerial lexicon. Hicks and Gullett (1987), cited in Enudu (1999), define strategy as the fundamental pattern of proposals and policies that define the firm and its business activities.

Project Implementation Strategy

From a process perspective, project strategy implementation is defined as the stage following the formal selection of a strategy, where broad objectives are translated into action plans, schedules, budgets, projects, and metrics (Claudiu, Flaviu, & Georgeta-Madalina, 2018). Harrington (2016) defines project strategy implementation as an iterative process that involves implementing strategies, policies, programs, and action plans allowing a firm to leverage its resources to seize opportunities in the competitive environment with physical projects (Thompson & Strickland, 2019).

Project Design

Project design management is a domain-specific approach to managing architectural design and construction projects in an ever-changing environment. Recent research highlights the importance of understanding projects, particularly building projects, as social systems in which there is a complex interplay and alignment of different goals, meanings, and perspectives (O'leary, 2018) (Svejvig, 2015).

Project Monitoring

Monitoring can be defined as the ongoing process through which stakeholders obtain regular feedback on the progress made toward achieving their goals and objectives. In contrast, evaluation is a rigorous and independent assessment of either completed or ongoing activities to determine the extent to which they are achieving stated objectives and contributing to decision-making (UNDP, 2019). Monitoring serves several purposes, including learning what works and what doesn't, making informed decisions regarding program operations and service delivery based on objective data, ensuring the effective and efficient use of resources, tracking program progress, assessing the extent to which the program is having its desired impact, fostering transparency, building public trust, understanding and meeting donor needs, and creating institutional memory.

Performance

McNamara (2018) defines performance as the completion of a mission involving the application of experience, skills, and abilities. Job performance in the workplace implies meeting predefined task function criteria, while citizenship performance involves a collection of individual activities and contributions (prosocial organizational behavior) that support the company's culture. Richard (2020) states that organizational performance includes three specific areas of firm outcomes: financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on investment, etc.), oil and gas performance (cost, time, quality, etc.).

Implementation Strategy and Performance

The role of strategy implementation is to translate plans into actions and intended results. The success of strategy implementation is measured by whether the actual oil and gas performance matches or exceeds the targets outlined in the strategic plan. Shortfalls in performance indicate either a weak strategy, weak implementation, or both. The effectiveness of implementing a particular strategy should significantly impact performance in the dimensions that the strategy is expected to influence (Venkatraman and Ramanujam, 2018).

Conceptual Framework

Orodho (2019) explains that a conceptual framework describes the relationship between research variables. Jabareen (2018) defines a variable as a measurable characteristic with different values among subjects. In this study, the independent variables include project implementation strategy, and the dependent variable is the performance of oil and gas-funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria.

Independent Variables

Dependent Variable

Figure 1: Model of Project Implementation Strategy and Performance of Oil and Gas.

Source: Adapted from Mukamugenga, A and Eugenia, I.N (2022). Project Implementation Practices and Project Performance in Rwanda: A case of Masaka Farm Supported by Africa to Africa Green Solutions, International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, 12(10), 12-22

Theoretical Framework

After reviewing several theories, this study is anchored in the Theory of Change and the Theory of Constraint as the theoretical underpinning for the research.

Resource-Based Theory (RBT)

The Resource-Based Theory was pioneered by Rumelt (Rumelt, 1984). This is an organizational management theory applied to identify the strategic resources available to an organization (Kavuvu, 2018). The theory posits that an organization's competitive advantage depends on how it utilizes its available resources (Werner, 2020). These resources include assets, capabilities, organizational processes, and attributes that enable the development and successful implementation of a strategy (Barney, 2019). The Holistic Strategy Implementation Theory presents various dimensions that can be assumed during strategy implementation. These models include the Chief Officer Model, which draws authority from the military, similar to the way a Chief Executive Officer (CEO) exerts full control, making strategic decisions but not participating in execution. The Theory of Change focuses on deliberate interventions in an organization's structure and systems to achieve the desired behavioral effects.

Theory of Change

This research employs the Theory of Change developed by Ellen in 2014. The Theory of Change helps define the needs to be addressed, the changes to be made, and the planned actions. It provides clarity on the outcome chain and the selected strategies (Harries, 2014). According to Paina (2017), the Theory of Change informs project implementation and innovation. The construction of a Theory of Change related to project implementation practices and project performance involves planning, communication, learning, and accountability. Planning the process, establishing timetables, forming a team, and articulating long-term outcomes aid in developing a Theory of Change based on project performance and execution.

Theory of Constraint

This study also utilizes the Theory of Constraint developed by Elsevier in 2014. The Theory of Constraints posits that a limited number of constraints impede any management system from achieving its goals. It identifies challenges and restructures to address them (Elsevier, 2014). The Triple Constraint Theory in project management emphasizes that every project operates within the scope, time, and cost constraints, where a change in one factor affects the others. It is essential for the manager to balance these aspects and manage expectations to achieve project performance (Van, 2012).

Empirical Review

Project Design and Performance of Oil and Gas Funded Projects

Heintz, Lousberg and Wamelink (2020) investigated designing project management in Nigeria. The aim of the study was to investigate designing project management. Assuming that project management is a form of solving wicked problems, the study propose a designerly way to solve these problems. To this end, we introduce the project design cycle, consisting of the elements awareness, design, performance and reflection. This cycle has been studied in a purely exploratory study. Result of the study is that these elements are sometimes recognized, sometimes not, that the order of these elements has been hardly recognized, that the difference between Reflection-in-action and Reflection-after-Action has been recognized and a distinction seems to occur between

a 'large' Project Design Cycle through the overall project management and a 'small' Project Design Cycle in the daily management.

Project Monitoring and Performance of Oil and Gas Funded Project

Mbit and Kiruja (2015) examined role of monitoring and evaluation on performance of public organization projects in Kenya. The aim of this study was to establish the role of monitoring and evaluation on performance of public organization projects in Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive survey. A sample of 81 respondents of the target population was considered by use of stratified sampling method. The primary data was collected through the use of questionnaires and secondary data was obtained from published documents to supplement the primary data. The variables namely human resource ,implementation strategy, training and planning were regressed and study findings showed that all independent variables significantly and positively influenced performance of Kenya Meat commission projects.

Project Implementation Strategy and Performance

Donwa and Mgbame (2015) examined corruption in the oil and gas industry: implication for economic growth in Nigeria. The paper examines corruption in oil and gas industry as implication for economic growth. Library research method was adopted or this study. The finding of the study is that the level of corruption in Nigeria has significant impact on economy growth.

Kiragu (2018) conducted a study at the level of the project implementation. The study was to investigate factors associate with control of project design calendar during the period of execution. The study showed that the main factors of the planned schedule control were the funders' policies, project complexity and its associated risks. Different factors cause challenges and failure to some projects during the initial phase of the implementation practices; project stakeholders evidenced that 10% of project implemented did not succeed due to the lack of proper project design and monitoring practices.

Luhangala and Anyieni (2019) explained strategy implementation on organisation performance in Kenya. The study endeavored to establish the effects of leadership style, school structures and resource allocation in successful implementation of the strategy on performance of public secondary school a case of Nyamira County. The study was anchored in resource dependency theory hat underscores how resources of organizations affect the behavior. The study was based on the stakeholder theory. The researcher used descriptive research design. The study established that organizational structure and top leadership influence influences implementation of strategy in public secondary schools in Nyamira County.

Ferreira, Vieira Neto and Batista (2019) examined critical success factors on project and process management in competitive strategy implementation in Brazil. The purpose of the study was to examine project and process management the critical success factors needed to implement a competitive strategy aiming to rank them and to recommend guidelines for a successful competitive strategy implementation. Results requirements raised in the literature were considered as critical success factors for competitive strategy implementation and the analysis of the professionals' answers made it possible to include a further 12 critical success factors.

Lucas (2019) examined strategy implementation practices and performance in international non-governmental organizations in Kenya. This study was set out to establish the relationship between strategy implementation practices and performance in international non-governmental organizations (INGOs) in Kenya. This relationship was also stated by Pearson's correlation analysis showing that strategy implementation practices had a significant positive relationship with strategy implementation.

Mukamugenga and Eugenia (2022) studied project implementation practices and project performance in Rwanda. The purpose of this research was to assess implementation practices and project performance. The research used a descriptive survey design. Results to the first objective was indicated that 53.8% agreed that Maska farm has good project scope, 60.6% agreed that project design is shared to all stakeholders involved in the project, 78.8% agreed that they have project work plan during project execution. Correlation analysis felt that a positive correlation between good project scope and project quality, the good project scope and project timely delivery was not correlated, the good project scope significantly correlated with project cost efficiency and effectiveness. Findings showed 65.7% strongly agreed with the creation of a good monitoring system, 65.7% agreed with good monitoring and evaluation reporting system.

Gaps in Empirical Review

Past studies have addressed project implementation strategy and performance in various sectors of the economy, but there is a lack of research in the oil and gas sector. Many existing studies have not considered certain variables. These studies reveal conceptual, contextual, and theoretical gaps, as very few have focused on project implementation strategy and performance in oil and gas funded projects. This study aims to fill these gaps.

Methodology

This study adopted a survey research design, which involves gathering data through questionnaires and interviews from a representative group. The study aimed to sample the opinions of respondents and draw inferences based on their views. Primary sources were used, and data was collected through questionnaires distributed to citizens of Niger Delta State who are above 18 years old. The population of the study consisted of ten major local government areas in Delta State that received federal funding for oil and gas projects. A sample size of 400 customers was determined using Yamane (1967). The questionnaire was designed with six general questions and response options including strongly agree (SA), agree (A), undecided (UD), strongly disagree (SD), and disagreed (D).

The validity of the study instrument was confirmed through a pilot test, and experts in the field assessed face and content validity. Reliability was addressed using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient, and data analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25.0. Hypothesis testing was performed using Spearman's rank correlation test.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

4.1 Data Presentation

Table 4.1 Copies of the Questionnaire Distributed and Returned

Respondents	Copies of Questionnaire Distributed	Copies Returned	Percentage Returned	Copies not Returned	Percentage not Returned
Citizens	400	380	95%	20	5%
Total	400	380	95%	20	5%

Source: Field Survey, 2023

From table 4.1 above, it shows that 380 copies of the questionnaire were duly completed and returned representing 95 percent, while 20 copies of the questionnaire were not duly completed and returned from the respondents representing 5 percent. Therefore, the total of 380 (95%) copies was brought back and gathered or arranged for the analyzing the data.

4.2 Data Analysis

Table 4.2 Bio-Data of Respondents

Citizens		
Option	Frequency	Percentage%
Gender		
Male	200	53%
Female	180	47%
Total	380	100
Age		
18-30	190	50%
31-43	140	37%
44-56	30	8%
57-69	15	4%
70 and above	5	1%
Total	380	100

Marital Status	130	34%
Single	250	66%
Married	380	100
Total		
Highest Ed Qualification		
Ph.D	20	5%
Masters	50	13%
First Degree	40	11%
OND/NCE	140	37%
SSCE	80	21%
FSLC	50	13%
Total	380	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

From table above, it was found for citizens that 53 percents of the respondents were male, 47 percents were female. 50 percents of the respondents were within the aged bracket of 18-30years, 37 percent of the respondents were within aged bracket of 31-43years, 8 percent of the respondents were within aged bracket of 44-56years, 4 percent of the respondents were within aged bracket of 57-69years and finally 1 percent of the respondents were within the aged bracket of 70years and above. 34 percent of the respondents were married and 66 percent of the respondents remain single. 5 percent of the respondents were Ph.D. holders, 13 percent of the respondents were masters’ holders, 11 percent of the respondents were first degree holders, 37 percent of the respondents were OND/NCE holders, 21 percent of the respondents were SSCE, and finally, 13 percent of the respondents were FLSC holders.

4.2.1 Test of Hypotheses

Tests for Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Project design does not significantly and positively relates with performance of oil and gas funded project in Niger Delta Region of South South, Nigeria.

H_{a1}: Project design significantly and positively relates with performance of oil and gas funded project in Niger Delta Region of South South, Nigeria.

Table 4.3: Correlation Analysis Result

Correlations		Performance		
Project Design	Pearson Correlation	1	.458**	.500**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	380	380	380

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the correlation result shown above, we have project design and performance of oil and gas funded project in Niger Delta, with a probability value of .000 and $r = .458$ which indicates that there was significant positive relationship between project design and performance of oil and gas funded project in Niger Delta Region of South South, Nigeria.

Decision for Hypothesis One

Evidence given probability value of .000 is less than 0.05 level of significant and coefficient value of .458. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate concluding that project design had significant positive relationship with and performance of oil and gas funded project in Niger Delta Region of South South, Nigeria.

Tests for Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Project monitoring does not significantly and positively relates with performance of oil and gas funded project in Niger Delta Region of South South, Nigeria.

H_{a2}: Project monitoring significantly and positively relates with performance of oil and gas funded project in Niger Delta Region of South South, Nigeria.

Table 4.4: Correlation Analysis Result

Correlations	Performance			
Project monitoring	Pearson Correlation	1	.457**	.510**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	380	380	380
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				

From the correlation result shown above, we have project monitoring and performance of oil and gas funded project in Niger Delta Region, with a probability value of .000 and $r = .457$ which indicates that there was significant positive relationship between project monitoring and performance of oil and gas funded project in Niger Delta Region of South South, Nigeria.

Decision for Hypothesis Two

Evidence given probability value of .000 is less than 0.05 level of significant and coefficient value of .457. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate concluding that project monitoring had significant positive relationship with performance of oil and gas funded project in Niger Delta Region of South South, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Objective One: Examining the Relationship Between Project Design and the Performance of Oil and Gas Funded Projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria.

The results of this study reveal a significant positive relationship between project design and the performance of oil and gas funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria. This finding aligns with the research by Heintz, Lousberg, and Wamelink (2020), who investigated project management design in Nigeria. The study showed that these elements are sometimes recognized, sometimes not, and that the order of these elements is often not well-defined. Furthermore, it recognizes a distinction between Reflection-in-Action and Reflection-after-Action, suggesting a difference between a "large" Project Design Cycle in overall project management and a "small" Project Design Cycle in daily management.

Objective Two: Establishing the Relationship Between Project Monitoring and the Performance of Oil and Gas Funded Projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria.

The results of this study indicate a significant positive relationship between project monitoring and the performance of oil and gas funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the study by Mbit and Kiruja (2015), which examined the role of monitoring and evaluation in the performance of public organization projects in Kenya. The study employed a descriptive survey and found that various variables, including human resources, implementation strategy, training, and planning, significantly and positively influenced the performance of Kenya Meat Commission projects.

Summary of Findings

- i. Project design demonstrated a significant positive relationship with the performance of oil and gas funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria ($r = 0.458$, $p < 0.05$).
- ii. Project monitoring exhibited a significant positive relationship with the performance of oil and gas funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria ($r = 0.457$, $p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that project implementation strategy exhibits a significant positive relationship with the performance of oil and gas funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria. Furthermore, it is concluded that project design and project monitoring also display significant positive relationships with the performance of oil and gas funded projects in the Niger Delta Region of South-South, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The study recommends that contractors assigned to oil and gas funded projects should diligently identify all key elements necessary for designing and monitoring projects, in order to benefit the government and the

stakeholders in the communities. Additionally, contractors should ensure the efficient development of team management, encompassing financial, human, and production teams. The findings suggest that an improvement in project team management practices is required to enhance project performance, alongside the well-being of the communities' citizens.

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